

ALGORITHM FOR FINDING K-SHORTEST PATHS IN A GIVEN DIRECTED GRAPH

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ABSTRACT--We describe a new algorithm to find the k shortest simple (loop less) paths in a directed graph and report on its implementation. Our algorithm is based on matrix or linked list representation of a directed graph. It uses stack to keep track of nodes visited and uses separate stacks for each node to maintain track of nodes visited in current path from that node among all nodes which are directly linked to that node. Algorithm covers all paths through which we can reach to given sink from a given source and finds current length of the path and uses insertion sort to insert the current path in the sorted paths list. This algorithm is not feasible to find single shortest path or less no. of shortest paths, rather it is best suitable to find all paths in ascending order of their lengths.

KEYWORDS:

Shortest Path, Weighted Path, Directed Graph, Simple Path

INTRODUCTION:

The k shortest paths problem is a natural and long studied generalization of the shortest path problem, in which not one but several paths in increasing order of length are sought. Given a directed

graph G with nonnegative edge weights, a positive integer k , and two vertices s and t , the problem asks for the k shortest paths from s to t in increasing order of length. It can also be stated as the k shortest paths problem is to list the k paths connecting a given source-

destination pair in the digraph with minimum total length or weight. It produces different paths between a pair of nodes in ascending order of their total length or weight. We require that the paths be *simple* (loop free). See Figure 1 for an example illustrating the difference between the k shortest paths problem with and without the simplicity constraint. (As the figure shows, even in graphs with non-negative weights, although *the* shortest path is always simple, the subsequent paths can have cycles.) The k shortest paths problem in which paths are not required to be simple turns out to be significantly easier.

Figure 1: The difference between simple and non-simple k shortest paths. The three *simple* shortest paths have lengths 6; 20 and 21, respectively. Without the simplicity constraint, paths may use the cycles $(a; b; a)$ and $(d; e; d)$, giving shortest paths of lengths 6; 8; 10.

The problem of determining the k shortest *simple* paths has proved to be more challenging. When graph is fully connected or connectivity is very high, most of the algorithms take exponential time complexity. We try to give less time complexity and will analyze complexity of proposed algorithm to find its time complexity.

MOTIVATION FOR K – SHORTEST PATHS:

ADDITIONAL CONSTRAINTS:

One may wish to find a path that satisfies certain constraints beyond having a small length, but those other constraints may be hard to optimize. For example, in power transmission route, a power line should connect its endpoints reasonably directly, but there may be more or less community support for one option or another. A typical solution is to compute several short paths and then choose among them by considering the other criteria.

MODEL EVALUATION:

Paths may be used to model problems that have known solutions, independent of the path formulation; for instance, in a k -shortest-path model of automatic translation between natural languages, a correct translation can be found by a human expert. By listing paths until this known solution appears, one can determine how well the model fits the problem, in terms of the number of incorrect paths seen before the correct path. This information can be used to tune the model as well as to determine the number of paths that need to be generated when applying additional constraints to search for the correct solution.

SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS:

By computing more than one shortest path, one can determine how sensitive the optimal solution is to

variation of the problem's parameters. In biological sequence alignment, for example, one typically wishes to see several "good" alignments rather than one optimal alignment; by comparing these several alignments, biologists can determine which portions of an alignment are most essential. This problem can be reduced to finding several shortest paths in a grid graph.

GENERATION OF ALTERNATIVES:

It may be useful to examine not just the optimal solution to a problem, but a larger class of solutions, to gain a better understanding of the problem. For example, the states of a complex system might be represented as a finite state machine, essentially just a graph, with different probabilities on each state transition edge. In such a model, one would likely want to know not just the chain of events most likely to lead to a failure state, but rather all chains having a failure probability over some threshold. Taking the logarithms of the transition probabilities transforms this problem into one of finding all paths shorter than a given length.

APPLICATIONS:

The applications of shortest path computations include situations in which an actual path is the desired output, such as robot motion planning, highway and power line engineering, and network connection routing. They include problems of scheduling such as critical path computation in PERT charts. Many optimization problems solved by dynamic programming or more complicated matrix searching techniques, such as the knapsack problem and length-limited Huffman coding, can be expressed as shortest path problems.

EXAMPLE:

(i)

(ii)

Figure 2: (i) Four shortest paths, $P_1; \dots; P_4$. (ii) The associated path branching structure.

GRAPH REPRESENTATION:

Given a graph represented in terms of matrix where nodes at rows and columns represents nodes and values represents either 0/1 to represent an edge or weight or length between 2 given nodes.

ALGORITHM:

INITIALIZATION:

1. Initialize stacks for each node, enter nodes which are directly connected to each node into its corresponding stack and initialize stack top.
2. Initialize stack for current path being tracked, enter SOURCE(s) into this current path stack.
3. Initialize a Queue to maintain node sequences that represents paths in ascending order of weights or length (it will be a matrix).
4. Initialize weight to zero.

TRACKING OF PATHS:

5. Repeat the steps until current path stack is not empty
6. Go to the stack of node which is currently pointed by current path stack pointer.
7. If that stack pointer is out of last node in stack, initialize pointer at top again, remove that node from current path stack, decrement current path stack pointer, remove

corresponding weight specified between these 2 nodes.

8. Else PUSH this new node in current path stack, add corresponding weight specified between these 2 nodes.
9. If this new node is SINK(t), PUSH current path stack in a row in matrix representing tracked paths at correct position according to weight, POP last 2 nodes i. e. SINK and its previous node, also remove their corresponding weights.

TERMINATION:

- 10 If current path stack empty, terminate.

OUTPUT:

Output is Queue of node sequences that represents paths in ascending order of weights or length which is a matrix.

ANALYSIS:

SPACE COMPLEXITY:

As this algorithm tries to implement shortest paths algorithm with minimum time complexity, we compromise with space. Each node requires stack containing nodes which are directly connected. Thus, if it is fully connected, space complexity is $O(n^3)$ otherwise $O(n^2 * e)$, where n is number of nodes and e is number of edges.

TIME COMPLEXITY:

As this algorithm uses backtracking, i. e. control does not pass to starting node once sink is reached, rather goes on removing nodes until node through which change in the path occurs is reached, it does not take

quadratic time complexity. Rather it takes complexity as $O(n \log n + e)$, where n is number of nodes while e is number of edges. Complexity increases considerably if number of edges increases. Extra time is taken to add tracked path in output matrix which can either be recorded using insertion sort or can be stored along with weights which can then be used to retrieve paths in ascending order of its total length.

CONCLUSION:

We have presented an algorithm to find k -shortest paths in a directed graph.

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